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CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR FORMING AND IMPLEMENTING INVESTMENT POLICY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS... 8 Abduvaliyev Sanjar Abdurahmanovich	8
EVALUATION OF MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY BASED ON BUDGETING IN ENERGY ENTERPRISES (A FACTOR ANALYSIS CASE OF "HUDUDGAZTA'MINOT" JSC)..... 17 Sobirov Shoyadbek Kurbonaliyevich	17
PORTFOLIO OF POSTAL SERVICES AND THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF ITS DIGITALIZATION23 Mamatkulov Gulom Rustamovich	23
OPTIMIZING THE BALANCE BETWEEN LIQUIDITY AND CREDIT RISKS IN ENSURING BANKING STABILITY 30 Anvarov Asliddin Nabijon ugli	30
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RENEWABLE ENERGY DEPLOYMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....34 Hamroyeva Sabina Ismoil qizi, Dilshod Anvarjonovich Ismailov	34
MODERN TRENDS AND EFFICIENCY OF LENDING TO AGRICULTURAL PRODUCERS IN UZBEKISTAN..39 Shamshetova Gulraushan Sarsenovna	39
ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN YOUTH EMPLOYMENT AND CRIME (CASE OF UZBEKISTAN) 42 Khusniddinova Gulnoza	42
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE INFRASTRUCTURE OF UZBEKISTAN'S FINANCIAL SYSTEM 47 Qobilova Nodira Qayumjon qizi, Normurodov Kh.E.	47
FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF INCREASING THE EXPORT CAPACITY OF THE REGION AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ITS APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN 52 Mamadzhanova Tuygunoy Akhmadzhanovna	52
INSTITUTIONAL APPROACH TO WASTE MANAGEMENT AND ITS ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY 56 Otbosarov Abrorbek Adhamjon o'g'li	56
LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX (LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX) MODEL IN POWER GRID ENTERPRISES.. 61 Khojimurodov Zukhriddin Shukurullo oglu	61
MICROPROJECTS AS A MEANS OF INCREASING THE FINANCIAL ACTIVITY AND LITERACY OF THE POPULATION 67 Irgashev Anvar Farxodovich	67
INSTITUTIONAL VA TEXNOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLAR SHAROITIDA INNOVATION BANK XIZMATLARINI JORIY ETISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH..... 74 Azlarova Aziza Axrorovna	74
PROBLEMS OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL CLUSTERS IN THE LIGHT INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN 80 Umarkulov Kodirjon Maxamadaminovich	80
DIGITAL FINANCIAL INCLUSION AS A DRIVER OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM GLOBAL TRENDS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR EMERGING ECONOMIES..... 84 Sabitov Oybek Abduganievich, Sattoriy Fayzullokh Abdijabbor ugli	84
PROPERTIES OF HEAVY CONCRETE DISPERSEDLY REINFORCED WITH NON-METALLIC FIBERS AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF CALCULATING CONCRETE STRUCTURES BASED ON THEM 90 Usmonova Durdona, Gulomova Dilnura	90
THE EFFECT OF STABLE AND DYNAMIC PRICING ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR 98 Anvar DEBERDIYEV	98
ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.. 102 M.O. Yo'ldoshova	102

PEDAGOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING POLITICAL SCIENCE AT HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	106
Rasulev Bobirjon Atkhamovich	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM FOR REGULATING NON-STANDARD EMPLOYMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESSES	110
Fayzullayev Nurulla Bakhromovich	
PRIORITIES FOR IMPROVING THE HEALTHCARE FINANCING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	117
Gulira'no Atabekovna Ruzmetova	
FACTORS AFFECTING TAX PAYMENT SYSTEMS, EXISTING PROBLEMS, AND THEIR CAUSES	124
Tangirqulov Gulom Baxtiyorovich	
EFFECTIVENESS OF ENVIRONMENTAL TAXES IN REDUCING CARBON EMISSIONS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN ECONOMETRIC APPROACH.....	129
Kuziboev Bekhzod Hamidovich	
WAYS TO DEVELOP QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN THE SILK INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMY	134
Bahriddinov Asror Rakhmatovich, Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
STATE OF LENDING TO SMALL BUSINESS PROJECTS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS AND ITS ECONOMIC-STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.....	138
Nargiza Norqobilova Abdiqodirovna	
CONCEPTUAL DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF ENSURING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN ENTERPRISES.....	143
Asomidinova Mohigulbonu Oybek kizi	
ORGANIZATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN NON-STATE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS .	148
Xojiboyev Muxiddin Shodimuxamedovich	
THE NATURE AND ESSENCE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES IN MASS MEDIA ORGANIZATIONS.....	151
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF ALGORITHMS FOR RECOVERING MISSING (NAN) VALUES IN INFORMATION SYSTEM DATA	156
Yarmatov Sherzodjon Shokir oglu, Orifov Oxunjon Fazliddinzoda	
ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES	167
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
IMPROVING LOAN PORTFOLIO QUALITY AND CREDIT RISK MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS	173
Turgunov Nodirbek Muminjanovich	
INNOVATION CAPABILITIES AND EXPORT PERFORMANCE: THE MEDIATING ROLES OF SUPPLY CHAIN INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION — EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	177
Mukhammadyaminova Shakhzoda	
URBAN PLANNING OF TRANSPORT INTERCHANGE HUBS NEAR TUBERCULOSIS CARE FACILITIES IN UZBEKISTAN	183
Gabibova Irina Vagifovna, Abdumuminova Diyora Gayratovna	
ADAPTING INTERNAL AUDIT STANDARDS IN BUDGET ORGANIZATIONS TO PUBLIC PROCUREMENT PRACTICES.....	192
Meliboyev Askar Eshmuratovich	
ECONOMETRIC EVALUATION OF INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN KHOREZM REGION	197
Otajanov Umid Abdullayevich	
SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF MODERN RECLAMATION AND GIS TECHNOLOGIES ON SALINE SOILS IN KARAKALPAKSTAN.....	205
Tajibaev Berdakh	
ISSUES REGARDING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE “TOLLING OPERATIONS” MODULE IN THE GOODS MOVEMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM UNDER THE CUSTOMS TERRITORY PROCESSING REGIME	212
Lutpullaev Shukrullo Kudratullaevich	

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN ENHANCING TOURISM-RELATED BUSINESSES IN UZBEKISTAN	218
Akmaljon Odilov	
INTERNATIONAL TRENDS OF DIGITALIZATION IN CUSTOMS MANAGEMENT	222
Radjapova Latofat Sardarovna	
THE ROLE OF TAX POLICY IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY	230
Dexkanova Shodiyona Kaxramon qizi	
PRACTICES IN ENTERPRISE COST STRUCTURE MANAGEMENT AND DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT	236
Aymukhammedova Amina Kakajanovna	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLOTHING MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	242
Axmedova Gaziza Azim kizi	
RECONCEPTUALIZING BUSINESS INCUBATORS IN STARTUP ECOSYSTEMS: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS	246
Gafujon Usmanov	
DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN MARKETING APPROACHES TO CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT IN RETAIL ENTERPRISES	257
Safarov Bakhtiyor Djurakulovich	
MECHANISMS FOR EVALUATING AND IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN THE PUBLIC TRANSPORT SECTOR	263
Berdiyorov Temur Azamatovich	
THE INFLUENCE OF HYDRODYNAMIC ASPECTS OF GROUNDWATER LEVEL RISE ON URBAN WATERLOGGING	268
B.D. Abdullaev, B.R. Nasibov, Sh.T. Irgashev, D. Abdullaev	
BASIC INFORMATION MODEL OF A DIGITAL OBJECT	277
Gulyamov Shukhrat Mannapovich, Karakhanova Alsu Muratalievna, Keldiyorov Sirojiddin Tura ugli, Zayniddinova Zebiniso Akmalovna	
COMPARATIVE LIFE CYCLE AND TECHNO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF SOLAR PANEL MATERIALS FOR SUSTAINABLE PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEMS	281
Urishev Omadjon, Kushakova Sarvinoz, Kamolboyev Sirojbek	
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR FORMING ECOLOGICALLY ORIENTED MANAGEMENT IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	294
Kholov Hamza Tajiddinovich	
INVESTIGATION OF GERMANIUM EXTRACTION TECHNOLOGY FROM TECHNOGENIC METALLURGICAL WASTE	301
Yormatov Dostonbek, Shodiyev Abbos, Muhammadiyev Elbek	
MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING RESOURCE EFFICIENCY AND OPTIMIZING PRODUCTION COSTS IN THE CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY	309
Utbasarov Doniyorjon Bakhtiyorovich	
THEORETICAL, PRACTICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF AUDITING THE ACTIVITIES OF ECONOMIC ENTITIES ON THE BASIS OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS	318
Mirzaeva Sabina Khushnudovna, Khaydarova Dildora Djakhongirovna	
THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES ON WOMEN'S LABOR IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES OF UZBEKISTAN UNDER INDUSTRY 4.0	322
Doniyorova Zukhrabonu Alisher qizi	
LEVEL OF ENSURING FOOD SECURITY: IMPLEMENTATION MECHANISMS AND INSTRUMENTS	328
Sodiqjon Qodirovich Mattiyev	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION, ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY, AND LOCALIZATION POLICY OF THE PUBLIC PROCUREMENT SYSTEM	334
Turabov Sarvar Abdumalikovich	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDAGI INNOVATSIYALAR IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASH VOSITASIDA	339
Bozorova Madina Raxmat qizi	

PROJECT-ORIENTED ESP32 IOT CURRICULUM WITH A SHARED-RESOURCE LABORATORY MODEL: DESIGN, IMPLEMENTATION, AND LESSONS LEARNED	344
Ulugbek Tursunaliyev, Lazizbek Yusupov	
FIVE-CRITERION METHODOLOGY OF INTERNAL CONTROL ENVIRONMENT ASSESSMENT IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	353
Babakulova Matluba Kurbannazarovna	
THE EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION-INDUSTRY INTEGRATION IN THE CONTEXT OF THE KNOWLEDGE ECONOMY.....	357
Uzaydullayev Sherzod Shukurullayevich	
MECHANISMS AND DIRECTIONS FOR DEEPENING REGIONAL INTEGRATION PROCESSES IN CENTRAL ASIA.....	361
Akbarova Kamola Akmaljonovna	
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN HEALTHCARE INSTITUTIONS	368
Saidov Suhrob Shodmonovich	
IMPROVING INVESTMENT ATTRACTION MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN'S SERVICE SECTOR: BARRIERS, OPPORTUNITIES, AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS.....	371
Shermatov Axror Abdixakimovich	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR FORMING CUSTOMS RISK PROFILE INDICATORS BASED ON MATHEMATICAL AND STATISTICAL METHODS	377
Niyazov Sherzod Shovkat ugli	
AN INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK FOR CRYPTO-ASSET REGULATION: ADDRESSING LEGAL UNCERTAINTY IN DIGITAL FINANCIAL SYSTEMS	385
Iminokhunov Abdukokhor A., Khakimov Abdurakhmon Mukhammad-Ali ugli	
THEORETICAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL-ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF THE SERVICE SECTOR	396
Kurbanova Rahima Jamshedovna	
REGIONAL ASSESSMENT OF THE OPENNESS OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON A SYNTHETIC INDICATOR.....	401
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifkhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
IMPROVEMENT OF THE REGIONAL INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT ASSESSMENT CRITERIA AND INDICATORS SYSTEM.....	407
Maxmudov Jasurbek Ergashevich	
ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN INVESTMENT ATTRACTION PRACTICES IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY.....	412
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli	
ASSESSMENT OF SOURCES OF EQUITY FORMATION IN JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THEIR USE.....	421
Savinova Galina Anatolevna	
DIGITAL MARKETING INTEGRATION, KPI ARCHITECTURE AND CAUSAL EVALUATION OF ENTERPRISE COMPETITIVENESS IN EMERGING MARKETS: A CONCEPTUAL-METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR UZBEKISTAN	429
Bakhtiyor Ruziev Eshmuminovich	
IMPROVING FOREIGN EXCHANGE RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN	434
B.K. Tugalov	
CHANGES IN THE BIOLOGICAL DIVERSITY OF HOOFED ANIMALS IN THE TUGAI FORESTS OF THE SOUTHERN ARAL REGION UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE CONDITIONS.....	438
J. U. Tilepov, A. A. Jumamuratova	
ECONOMETRIC ASSESSMENT MECHANISMS OF THE IMPACT OF TRADE SERVICE QUALITY INDICATORS ON THE LEVEL OF COMPETITIVENESS	442
Toxirov Javlon Raximovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BIZNES MUHITINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING AHAMIYATI ..	447
Xazratov Abror Panjiyevich, Muratkulov Xumoyun Dilshodovich	

LEGAL FOUNDATIONS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COTTON PROCESSING INDUSTRY IN BUSINESS ENTITIES	452
Abdullayev Hamidulla Abdug'ani o'g'li, Sayitbayev Shermirza Datkamirzayevich	
BALANCING ECONOMIC GROWTH AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION IN TOURISM.....	456
Kamalova Malika Umidjanovna, Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF A MODEL FOR IMPROVING FACE-ID TECHNOLOGY IN ENSURING INFORMATION SECURITY ON E-PLATFORMS.....	462
Maxamadov Rustam Xabibullayevich, Djamatov Mustafa Xatamovich	
SOLIQLAR VA DAVLAT BUDJETI: SOLIQ TIZIMINING BUDJETIGA TA'SIRI.....	467
Izbosarov Bobur Baxriddinovich, Umirov Sherzod Baxriddinovich	
СИСТЕМНЫЕ ОГРАНИЧЕНИЯ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ БАНКОВСКОГО СЕКТОРА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	472
Аширкулов Диорбек Алишер угли, Каримова Азиза Махомадризовна	
THE IMPACT OF INFLATION ON THE ECONOMY AND WAYS TO REDUCE IT	479
Abdullaeva Zulfiya Izzatovna, Ashurova Jasmina Jora qizi	
КОЛЛИЗИИ ГРАЖДАНСКОГО И СЕМЕЙНОГО ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВА В ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СУПРУГОВ.....	483
Рашидова Зилола Жавлонбековна	
SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES (SME) AND DISTRICT-LEVEL PANEL DATA ANALYSIS IN THE CONTEXT OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	487
Ismoilov Elyorjon Makhamadali ugli, Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND ONLINE PLATFORMS IN THE TOURISM SECTOR.....	495
Bakayev Ziyovuddinxon Toshbolta o'g'li	
CHINA'S DIGITAL YUAN (E-CNY) PROJECT: ANALYSIS OF THE INTERNATIONAL CONTEXT, PRACTICAL EXPERIENCE, AND POSSIBILITIES OF IMPLEMENTATION IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN.....	500
Tashquziyev Suxrob Abdurazzak ugli	
VALYUTA KURSI REJIMLARI (ERKIN SUZUVCHI, BOG'LANGAN, ARALASH): MILLIY VALYUTA BARQARORLIGIGA TA'SIRINI NAZARIY SOLISHTIRISH.....	505
G'afurov Olimjon G'olib o'g'li	
IMPACT OF DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN UZBEKISTAN, STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND TRENDS	510
Ibodullayev Navro'zbek Ikram o'g'li, Akbarov Nodir G'ofurovich	
THE IMPACT OF INFRASTRUCTURE-ORIENTED FISCAL POLICY ON REGIONAL COMPETITIVENESS.....	517
Ne'matov Ne'matulla Erkinboyevich	
BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA ICHKI AUDIT METODOLOGIYASI: XALQARO STANDARTLAR VA MILLIY AMALIYOTNING QIYOSIY TAHLILI.....	523
Saitmuratov Saitmuarat Masharip o'g'li	
AHOLINING BANKLARDAGI OMONATLARINI KAFOLATLASH MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	528
Rahimov Akmal Matyaqubovich	
ISSUES IN DETERMINING THE MATERIALITY LEVEL IN AUDIT FIRMS.....	536
Pirnazarova Juldiz Djamiljan qizi	
IMPROVING THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF COMMERCIAL BANK BUSINESS MODELS: THEORY AND PRACTICE	543
O.O. Khudayarov	

IMPROVING THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF COMMERCIAL BANK BUSINESS MODELS: THEORY AND PRACTICE

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Abstract: This article examines the issues of digital transformation of business models in commercial banks of Uzbekistan. The evolutionary stages of global banking practice from Bank 1.0 to Bank 4.0, the theoretical foundations of the business model concept, the current state of Uzbekistan's banking system, and the key barriers to transformation are analyzed. Based on the research findings, scientific proposals and practical recommendations have been developed for improving the business models of commercial banks.

Keywords: commercial bank, business model, digital transformation, Bank 4.0, fintech, open banking, platform economy, Uzbekistan banking system.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O'zbekiston tijorat banklari biznes modellarining raqamli transformatsiyasi masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Jahon bank amaliyotida Bank 1.0 dan Bank 4.0 gacha bo'lgan evolyutsion rivojlanish bosqichlari, biznes modeli tushunchasining nazariy asoslari, O'zbekiston bank tizimidagi hozirgi holat hamda transformatsiyaning asosiy to'siqlari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot natijalari asosida tijorat banklari biznes modellarini takomillashtirish bo'yicha ilmiy taklif va amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tijorat banki, biznes modeli, raqamli transformatsiya, Bank 4.0, fintech, ochiq banking, platforma iqtisodiyoti, O'zbekiston bank tizimi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассмотрены вопросы цифровой трансформации бизнес-моделей коммерческих банков Узбекистана. Проанализированы эволюционные этапы развития мировой банковской практики от Bank 1.0 до Bank 4.0, теоретические основы концепции бизнес-модели, современное состояние банковской системы Узбекистана, а также основные барьеры трансформации. На основе результатов исследования разработаны научные предложения и практические рекомендации по совершенствованию бизнес-моделей коммерческих банков.

Ключевые слова: коммерческий банк, бизнес-модель, цифровая трансформация, Bank 4.0, финтех, открытый банкинг, платформенная экономика, банковская система Узбекистана.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the global financial system is undergoing extensive transformations driven by the rapid advancement of digital technologies, the integration of artificial intelligence into banking processes, the growing competition from fintech companies, and fundamental changes in consumer behavior. These developments necessitate a reconsideration of commercial bank business models from a new perspective. According to data from the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, more than 65 percent of banking transactions were conducted in digital format in 2025. This indicates a significant expansion in technological adaptability, operational efficiency, and remote service capabilities within the banking sector.

In the context of the digital economy, traditional business models of commercial banks have begun to lose their effectiveness. A model based solely on physical branches and conventional lending-deposit operations can no longer meet the demands of today's rapidly changing market environment. The rapid growth of new-generation banks such as TBC Bank, Anorbank, and Uzum Bank in Uzbekistan demonstrates that this transformation is becoming inevitable within the national banking system as well.

The number of customers using remote banking services increased from 14.5 million in 2020 to 52.9 million in 2025, representing a 3.6-fold increase in less than five years. Such rapid growth requires commercial banks to promptly enhance their digital infrastructure, service delivery channels, and business processes. The purpose of this article is to identify the theoretical and methodological foundations of commercial bank business model transformation, analyze the current state and challenges of Uzbekistan's banking system, and develop practical recommendations for its further improvement.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The concept of the “business model” was significantly influenced by the renowned economist Peter Drucker. According to Drucker, a business model represents a set of assumptions related to identifying target market segments, competitors, customer needs, and the strengths and weaknesses of a company [1]. Paul Timmers was among the first scholars to define and classify business models individually. In his view, business models constitute a framework of products, services, and information flows that includes descriptions of the roles of various participants, potential benefits, and sources of revenue [2].

The “Business Model Canvas” approach developed by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur is considered one of the most widely used conceptual tools in modern business model theory. According to the authors, a business model is a logical structure that systematically describes how an enterprise or organization creates value, delivers that value to customers, and captures economic benefits from it [3]. This framework consists of nine key building blocks: value proposition, customer segments, distribution channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partners, and cost structure.

In his book *Bank 4.0*, Brett King categorizes the evolution of banking into four stages. King interprets banks not merely as licensed financial institutions but as high-tech companies centered on user experience. Through the principle “Banking is no longer somewhere you go, but something you do,” he completely separates banking services from the traditional concept of a physical location [4]. Dirk Zetsche and his co-authors describe digital transformation in banking as a transition from vertically integrated models to decentralized platforms based on APIs and digital ecosystems [5].

Among local researchers, A. Erdonayev interprets banking transformation as a process of fundamentally reconsidering a bank’s entire business model. His approach emphasizes the development of a flexible banking management system that is customer-oriented, integrated with digital technologies, and capable of responding rapidly to changes in the external environment [6]. O. Shoymardonov highlights the necessity of building business ecosystems within commercial banks, emphasizing that banking services should be integrated around a unified digital platform rather than being offered as isolated products and services [7].

A financial report by PwC highlights the growing convergence between fintech and traditional banking. According to the report, by 2023 more than 85 percent of banks worldwide had implemented elements of digital transformation, including remote identification, automated lending, voice interfaces, and robo-advisory services [8]. Research conducted by McKinsey indicates that the effective application of artificial intelligence can reduce banking operational costs by approximately 15–20 percent [9].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed several scientific methods. The comparative analysis method was used to examine and compare the business models of commercial banks in different countries and in Uzbekistan. The methods of abstraction and generalization were applied to formulate the theoretical foundations of banking business models. Statistical analysis was utilized to examine the dynamics of Uzbekistan’s banking system during the period 2020–2025. A systems approach was employed to comprehensively evaluate the structural elements of commercial bank business models. SWOT and GAP analysis techniques were used to identify existing disparities and development gaps within Uzbekistan’s banking system.

The empirical basis of the study consists of official reports of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, analytical materials published by PwC and McKinsey, statistical data from the Ministry of Digital Technologies, and financial reports of commercial banks operating in Uzbekistan. The research, conducted on the basis of a monographic approach, covers the digital development indicators of 12 major commercial banks in Uzbekistan during the period from 2020 to 2025.

TAHLIL VA NATIJALAR

The evolution of banking business models encompasses the transformation from traditional service centers into intelligent ecosystems seamlessly integrated into customers’ daily lives. This transformation has not only changed the channels through which banking products are delivered but has also diversified banks’ sources of revenue generation. Table 1 presents a comparative overview of the evolutionary stages of banking business models.

Table 1. Evolutionary Stages of Banking Business Models¹

Stage	Model Description	Main Channel	Efficiency
Bank 1.0	Traditional model	Physical branches	60–70% of costs allocated to personnel and facilities
Bank 2.0	Self-service model	ATMs and internet banking	30% reduction in transaction costs
Bank 3.0	Mobile banking	Smartphones and mobile applications	More than 80% of customers prefer remote services
Bank 4.0	Ecosystem and AI	Real-time platforms	Up to 40% of revenue generated from non-banking services

At the Bank 4.0 stage, banking operations become closely interconnected with artificial intelligence, big data analytics, automated decision-making, biometric identification, open APIs, and ecosystem-based financial services. At this stage, a bank is no longer merely an institution that responds to customer requests; rather, it becomes a digital partner capable of analyzing customers' financial behavior, purchasing habits, and life circumstances in order to proactively offer relevant services before they are explicitly requested.

Digital transformation within Uzbekistan's banking system has accelerated significantly over the past five years. According to the Ministry of Digital Technologies, investments directed toward digital infrastructure increased from USD 80 million in 2020 to USD 180 million in 2025. This 2.25-fold growth demonstrates the strengthening strategic focus on digital development within the banking sector.

Several key trends can be observed in the digital development of Uzbekistan's commercial banks. First, the emergence and rapid expansion of neobanks such as TBC Bank, Anorbank, and Uzum Bank. Second, the modernization of mobile applications by traditional banks, including Xalq Banki and Ipoteka Bank. Third, the expansion of integration among interbank payment systems such as HUMO and UzCard. Fourth, the introduction of regulatory documents by the Central Bank aimed at promoting Open Banking initiatives.

Research indicates that financial intermediaries operating exclusively in the digital environment and relying on nonlinear business models demonstrate the highest annual gross revenue growth rate, reaching 76 percent, whereas traditional vertically integrated financial institutions achieve only 44 percent growth. Financial intermediaries utilizing digital technologies and nonlinear models are considerably ahead of traditional banks in terms of product modularization and adaptability to value-chain fragmentation.

In the process of improving commercial bank business models through digital transformation in Uzbekistan, several promising development directions are emerging. These can be analyzed through the following categories.

First, the gradual harmonization of digital infrastructure is creating broad opportunities for the development of the technological platform component of banking business models. The acceleration of integration processes among interbank information systems, payment platforms, and external fintech services is establishing a solid foundation for the transition toward open banking, digital ecosystems, and platform-based financial service models. While the average platformization level of banking ecosystems in developed countries reaches approximately 90 percent, this indicator in Uzbekistan is estimated at around 40 percent, demonstrating substantial growth potential for the future.

Second, the continuous improvement of digital literacy and professional competencies is strengthening business model components related to customer segments and human capital. By enhancing customers' ability to utilize digital services, banks can further increase the economic efficiency of services such as mobile applications, internet banking, online lending, and remote identification.

Third, the adaptation of the regulatory and legal environment to technological changes contributes to strengthening the institutional foundations of banking business models. Further development of the legal framework governing digital banking products, fintech partnerships, remote identification, electronic contracts, open data exchange, and the application of artificial intelligence creates important opportunities for enhancing the innovative capacity of the banking sector.

Fourth, the steady improvement of regional digital development levels contributes to expanding service delivery channels and customer outreach within commercial banking business models. As telecommunications infrastructure continues to modernize, access to mobile banking, internet banking, QR payments, and remote lending services is becoming increasingly widespread. While API openness averages approximately 85 percent in developed markets, it is estimated at around 35 percent in Uzbekistan, indicating considerable potential for future development in this area.

¹ Source: Compiled by the author.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the conducted research, the following conclusions have been drawn:

The business model of commercial banks in modern conditions is a complex economic system that extends beyond traditional lending and deposit operations, incorporating digital platforms, fintech partnerships, ecosystem-based services, and Big Data-driven management decisions. The Bank 4.0 concept demonstrates the transition of banking services from a physical environment to a digital space and subsequently to a platform-based model integrated into customers' everyday activities.

Digital transformation has become an irreversible evolutionary process within Uzbekistan's banking system. The number of users of remote banking services increased by 3.6 times between 2020 and 2025, reaching 52.9 million people. More than 65 percent of banking transactions are now conducted in digital format.

To improve the business models of commercial banks in Uzbekistan, the following measures are necessary: expanding investments in digital infrastructure and strengthening interbank integration; implementing Open Banking standards and developing API integration; updating the regulatory framework related to digital identification, cybersecurity, and data protection; expanding digital literacy programs for both customers and banking personnel; and developing public-private partnership mechanisms aimed at reducing regional digital disparities.

The study demonstrates that banks that have transitioned to nonlinear digital business models achieve revenue growth rates approximately 1.7 times higher than those operating under traditional models. This indicates that digital transformation has become not only a necessity but also a key factor in maintaining the competitiveness of commercial banks in Uzbekistan.

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